

Digital Entrepreneurship and Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) Performance in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of digital entrepreneurship on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Osun State, Nigeria. A survey research design was employed, and data were collected from 245 SME respondents across the Production, Trading, and Services sectors using structured questionnaires. Descriptive analysis revealed widespread adoption of digital entrepreneurship tools. Multiple regression results showed that E-commerce adoption ($t = 6.64$, $\beta = 0.296$), digital services ($t = 7.45$, $\beta = 0.313$) and software development ($t = 6.73$, $\beta = 0.353$) all had positive influence on SME performance, with digital services exerting the strongest impact. SMEs leveraging these tools reported improved operational efficiency, improved customer engagement, and increased financial performance. The results further highlighted the importance of contextual factors such as infrastructure quality, market readiness, and user capabilities in promoting the benefits of digital adoption. In conclusion, the study demonstrated that strategic adoption and integration of digital entrepreneurship tools, combined with skills development and supportive infrastructure, can enhance SME performance and competitiveness in Osun State. It recommended that policymakers, SME owners, and technology providers collaborate to strengthen digital literacy, optimize digital services, and improve enabling infrastructure to maximize performance outcomes, sustain growth, and foster long-term resilience.

JEL Classification: L26, M13, O33, L25, O31

Keywords: Digital entrepreneurship, E-commerce, Digital services, Software development, SMEs performance.

Introduction:

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) serve as a backbone of national economies, especially through their capacity to drive economic growth, generate employment opportunities, and stimulate innovation (World Bank, 2020). Even with their importance, SMEs often face challenges such as limited access finance, inadequate infrastructure, and low digital literacy, which impeded their ability to adopt digital technologies and improve competitiveness (Aina, Ifeoluwa, & Uwitonze, 2022; Okunlola, 2024). However, with the pace of technological change, to maintain competitive edge SMEs must embrace digital transformation to tackle challenges effectively (Bouwman et al., 2019; Kraus et al., 2021).

Digital entrepreneurship refers to the process of establishing and operating business activities through digital technologies and online platforms, often without the need for extensive physical infrastructure (Nambisan, 2017). Examples include e-commerce ventures, online education platforms, content creation outlets like blogs and YouTube channels, and digital service providers. It reflects the ongoing evolution of entrepreneurship, shaped by advancements in technology and digital ecosystems (Nambisan, 2017). In addition, Manjon et al. (2022) emphasize that digital entrepreneurship is recognized as a catalyst for innovation and economic transformation in the digital. It is sometimes described as e-commerce, cyber entrepreneurship, or internet-based enterprise, covering both newly established businesses and the digital modernization of existing firms through innovative technologies (Nambisan, 2017).

In today's rapidly evolving digital economy, technology has become a key driver of business transformation, particularly for Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), which contribute significantly to economic growth, job creation, and innovation in developing countries like Nigeria (Nambisan, 2017). This study focuses primarily on the effect of digital entrepreneurship on small and medium enterprises performance in Osun State, which operate in diverse sectors including production, trading, and services sectors. These businesses often face structural barriers such as poor infrastructure, limited technical knowledge, low digital literacy, and the high cost of digital tools, which hinder full digital adoption and limit their potential for performance growth (Aina, Ifeoluwa, & Uwitonze, 2022; Oseni, 2024). Research shows that e-commerce adoption improves market reach and customer engagement. In addition, Adebayo and Ayeni (2022) reported increased sales among Lagos-based SMEs using digital platforms, despite infrastructure-related challenges. Ogundele and Eromonsele (2020) also found that digital adoption enhances competitiveness; however, it remains limited in semi-urban regions due to infrastructural and literacy constraints. The usage of platforms like WhatsApp, Jumia, Konga, and TikTok among Osun SMEs remains underexplored (Adelakan, 2023).

Digital services such as online bookings and virtual customer support are reshaping service delivery. Ghazawneh (2019) observed that limited skills and readiness in less

developed areas hinder innovation. Yet, SMEs in Osun still rely on traditional service models due to low awareness and capability, and few studies have explored their adoption of digital service models (Apulu & Latham, 2011; Okundaye, Fan, & Dwyer, 2019). Osun SMEs face an uneven pace of digital adoption due to structural barriers such as limited internet access, low digital skills, high device costs, and weak support systems. Consequently, tools like e-commerce, digital services and software development solutions remain underutilized. While the general benefits of digital innovation are well-documented, few studies have examined how digital entrepreneurship influences the performance of SMEs in Osun State. (Ogundele & Eromonsele, 2020; Global System for Mobile Communications Association, 2023).

This study seeks to fill this gap by exploring how digital entrepreneurship including e-commerce, digital services and software development solutions affects the performance of small and medium enterprises SMEs across selected LGAs in Osun State. The findings seek to guide policymakers, stakeholders, and SME owners in designing approaches that support digital inclusion, competitiveness, and sustainable growth in semi-urban areas (Adewoye, 2020). Understanding these dynamics will help identify how digital entrepreneurship tools can improve SMEs performance, and which tools offer the greatest impact on sales, operational efficiency, business growth, expansion and competitiveness. The broad objective of the study is to examine the impact of digital entrepreneurship on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Osun State. The specific objectives which are to:

- i. examine the effect of e-commerce on the performance of SMEs in Osun State.
- ii. ascertain the relationship between digital service and the performance of SMEs in Osun State.
- iii. assess the relationship between software development solutions and the performance of SMEs in Osun State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Digital Entrepreneurship: Manjon et al (2022) assert that digital entrepreneurship has been identified as a fundamental driver of modern technology, innovation, and entrepreneurial activities in the digital age. Digital entrepreneurship refers to the integration of digital tools in creating new businesses or modernizing existing ones through the adoption of digital platforms and tools (Bogachov et al., 2021). Digital entrepreneurship has become a critical area of study in the digital age because it enables enterprises, especially small and medium-sized enterprise (SMEs), to leverage digital platforms and technologies to create value, enhance market access, and improve operational efficiency (Wodu et al., 2024; Nwawume & Anukam, 2024).

E-commerce: Electronic commerce has reshaped how businesses conduct transactions and interact with customers in the global marketplace (Laudon & Traver, 2021; Chaffey, 2015). E-commerce involves using electronic platforms like the internet and computer networks to exchange products and services (Akande & Akintunde 2018). The adoption of e-commerce has become essential for enhancing operational efficiency and competitiveness, particularly because SMEs contribute to employment generation and overall economic growth (Adeleke et al., 2018). Furthermore, Olanrewaju et al. (2020) note that mobile applications and social networking sites have increasingly become standard platforms for MSMEs to conduct business.

Digital Services: Digital services refer to as technology enabled services delivered through digital platforms to enhance accessibility, efficiency, and interaction in both business and educational Rust and Huang (2014) describe digital services as technology-enabled services provided through the internet or other electronic communication channels.

Software Development Solutions: Software development plays a fundamental role in enabling innovation and digital transformation across industries. (Baskerville et al., 2020). Software development and digital solutions are increasingly recognized as key tools that enable (SMEs) to improve operational efficiency, enhance service delivery, and expand market opportunities (Afolabi et al., 2019; Olanrewaju et al., 2020). Current studies shows that software development is not just a technical task but a strategic enabler for organizational growth, innovation, and customer engagement (Nguyen-Duc et al., 2020).

SMEs Performance: The performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) has been widely explored across various disciplines because of its role in driving economic development, employment generation, and innovation, especially in developing countries. (Beck et al., 2005; Abor & Quartey, 2010; Ayyagari et al., 2011). Aremu et al (2019), emphasize that SME performance includes indicators such as profitability, efficiency, growth, revenue, market share, and competitiveness.

Theoretical Review

Resource-Based View (RBV): The Resource-Based View (RBV), propounded by Jay Barney (1991), posits that an organisation's internal resources and capabilities are the important determinants of sustained competitive advantage and firm performance. The theory emphasises that only resources that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) can yield lasting advantage. In the context of digital entrepreneurship, the theory explains how technologies such as e-commerce platforms, digital services, digital content creation, software development, and social media entrepreneurship serve as strategic assets for SMEs, enabling them to access new markets, reach wider audiences, and improve performance (Wernerfelt, 1984; Raji et al., 2024). (Zhao, 2021; Baig et al., 2022;

Ogundele & Eromonsele, 2020) affirm that adopting digital tools enhances SMEs' operational efficiency, revenue growth, and competitiveness, confirming RBV's relevance in explaining how digital technologies strengthen firm performance

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM): The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis (1989), explains that individuals' adoption of technology is primarily influenced by two key perceptions: Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU). In the SME context, TAM provides insight into how perceptions of usefulness and ease of use influence the adoption of digital tools such as e-commerce platforms, digital services, and software applications, thereby improving business operations and customer engagement. Extensions of the model, such as those by Galan et al. (2013) and Al-Ghaili, Mahomed, and Yusof (2024), integrate constructs like trust, social image, and government support, showing that contextual and behavioural factors also mediate technology adoption. Thus, TAM remains a valid and adaptable model for analysing technology acceptance and digital transformation among SMEs, particularly in developing economies. Together the two theories link resource value with technology adoption behaviour, providing a robust framework for understanding SME performance.

Theoretical Framework: This study is underpinned by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), proposed by Davis (1989). The model recognises that users' perceptions of a technology's usefulness (PU) and ease of use (PEOU) influence their attitudes, intentions, and actual adoption behavior. In the context of digital entrepreneurship, SMEs are more likely to adopt tools such as e-commerce platforms, digital services, software solutions, and social media when they perceive them as beneficial and easy to operate. Platforms like WhatsApp, Instagram, and Jumia are embraced when they enhance customer reach and sales with minimal effort. TAM thus explains how SMEs' perceptions of practicality and simplicity mediate the relationship between digital entrepreneurship tools and SME performance, particularly in developing economies like Nigeria (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000; Alalwan et al., 2017; Oladele & Abiodun, 2020).

Empirical Review: Edokobi et al. (2022), examined how e-commerce influences SME performance in Anambra State through the application of the Vector Autoregression (VAR) model. Their study considered variables such as online sales, digital marketing, e-payment adoption, website quality, and social media use. The findings indicated that online sales, digital marketing, e-payment systems, and website quality significantly enhanced the operational efficiency of SMEs. In contrast, social media engagement had no statistically significant direct impact (Edokobi et al., 2022). The study recommended that SMEs invest in e-commerce infrastructure, enhance digital marketing strategies, adopt e-payment systems, and improve website quality to sustain and enhance operational efficiency.

Ochinanwata and Ochinanwata (2023), carried out a qualitative study to examine the

impact of digital platforms on the development of online micro and small enterprises in Nigeria. The study aimed to understand how digital platforms enable business creation, support growth, and the challenges entrepreneurs face in adopting these platforms (Ochinanwata and Ochinanwata, 2023). The study revealed that customer trust plays a central role, with many entrepreneurs using videos and real-time engagement to build confidence in an environment plagued by fake products and imposters. The study suggests that both formal and informal educational and training institutions should integrate digital skills development into their programs to prepare aspiring entrepreneurs for the effective use of digital platforms in running and growing micro and small businesses in Nigeria.

Omulo and Noor (2023) investigated the influence of software development projects on how SMEs operate and succeed in Nairobi City County, Kenya. The study focused on the effects of programming languages and project platforms on SME performance, guided by the Institutional Leadership Theory and Stakeholder Theory. The findings revealed a strong and significant relationship between programming languages and SME performance. Based on the results, the researchers recommended that software developers conduct market surveys to better understand and meet customer needs. Despite the benefits of digital entrepreneurship most studies focus on developed or urban areas, with limited evidence from regions like Osun State, Nigeria, where SMEs adopt tools informally via WhatsApp, Facebook, free software. Additionally, studies rarely separate the effects of specific digital entrepreneurship tools, leaving unclear which activities most influence SME performance. This study addresses these gaps by examining e-commerce, digital services, and software development, providing contextual insights for SMEs in resource limited markets.

Methodology

The study utilised a survey research design to structure the research and show how all the major parts of this study and methods of the research work together to address the research questions. The target population consists of all registered SMEs operating within the (12) Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Osun State. According to the National MSME Survey Report (2017), the selected 12 LGAs had a total of 3,007 registered small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The total population for the study was 3007 SMEs. (SMEDAN & NBS, 2017). Using Raosoft formular, a sample of 246 SMEs was determined, providing adequate representation at a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error. To select the sample, two stage sampling technique was employed. In the first stage, four Local Government Areas (LGAs per each senatorial district) were selected from the 30 LGAs in Osun State using purposive sampling based on their level of commercial activity. This selection was guided by available data such as SME registration records, market density and business activity reports from SMEDAN as of December 2023 to focus on areas where SMEs are most concentrated and economically active, and where digital

entrepreneurship practices are more likely to be observed. The 12 selected LGAs represent economically active areas across the three senatorial districts, ensuring adequate geographical representation while focusing on locations with high SME concentration and business activity. In the second stage SMEs within the selected LGAs were Stratified according to business type: Production, Manufacturing, Trading and Services using a stratified random sampling after which samples were randomly selected from each stratum. This ensured that key SME sectors were adequately represented, reduced sampling bias, and enhanced the reliability and generalizability of the findings. A structured questionnaire served as the primary research instrument. This choice was justified by the need to systematically gather quantitative data from a large sample, ensuring consistency and reliability in responses. The data collected were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics summarized the demographic characteristics of respondents, while regression analysis was employed to test the study hypotheses related to each objective. **Cronbach's alpha method was employed.** A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.70 or above was considered acceptable, indicating that the instrument demonstrates a high level of internal consistency and was suitable for data collection and analysis.

Table 1 Reliability of Instruments

Variables	Items
E-commerce	7	0.83	
Digital Services	5	0.79	
Software Development	6	0.89	
SMEs Performance	6	0.80	

The data were processed electronically using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The analytical tool for each objective is as follows: Regression analysis was used to evaluate how the use of e-commerce adoption (via platforms like WhatsApp, Jumia, and Facebook) on SME performance. In addition, Pearson Correlation analysis was applied to examine the strength and the direction of the relationship between the use of digital services, software tools such as online tutoring, virtual assistant work, graphics designing and IT/web support custom-built apps, inventory /accounting software and SME performance indicators including operational/work efficiency and service delivery. The Model Specification are :

$$Y = \alpha + \beta X + U \quad \text{- Equation 3.1}$$

Y = SMEs Performance

α = Intercept (constant term)

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6$ = Coefficients of digital entrepreneurship variables

(measuring their individual impact on SME performance)

X_1 = E-commerce

X_2 = Digital Services

X_3 = Software Development U = Error term

Objective 1: To examine the effect of e-commerce adoption on the performance of SMEs in Osun State.

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + U \quad -$$

Equation 3.2

Where:

X_1 = WhatsApp

X_2 = Instagram

X_3 = TikTok

X_4 = Facebook

X_5 = Jumia

X_6 = Konga

β_1 to β_6 = Coefficients for each platform

U = Error term

Objective 2: To ascertain the relationship between digital services and SME performance in Osun State.

Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) will be used to assess the strength and direction of the linear relationship between each digital service and SME performance.

X_1 = Online Tutoring

X_2 = Virtual Assistant Services

X_3 = Graphics Design

X_4 = Web Design / IT Support

Interpretation of Pearson's r:

$r = +1$: Perfect positive correlation (as digital service usage increases, SME performance increases)

$r = -1$: Perfect negative correlation (as digital service usage increases, SME performance decreases)

$r = 0$: No linear relationship

Objective 3: To assess the relationship between software development usage

and SME performance in Osun State.

Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was applied to examine the linear relationship between software development tools and SME performance.

X = Custom-built Mobile Apps

X = Business Management Software

X = Website Development

X = Inventory/Accounting Software

Interpretation of Pearson's r:

r = +1: Perfect positive correlation

r = -1: Perfect negative correlation

r = 0: No linear relationship

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Testing of Hypotheses: This section deals with examination of the relationship that exist between the variables identified in the study as stated in the research objectives, research questions and the hypothesis. The model formulated earlier is tested using the simple linear regression. **Testing of Hypothesis One (H_{01}): E-commerce adoption has no significant effect on the performance of SMEs in Osun State.**

Table 1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.506a	.256	.123	.947

Predictors: (Constant), E-commerce

Table 2: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	74.87	1	74.87	83.3448	.000b
Residual	217.91	243	0.897		
Total	292.78	244			

Dependent Variable: SMEs Performance

Predictors: (Constant), E-commerce

Table 3: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.870	.061		30.66	.000
E-commerce	0.296	.0446	0.506	6.64	.000

Dependent Variable: Performance

Predictors: (Constant), E-commerce

Sources: Authors Computation, 2025.

Testing of Hypothesis One (H_{01}): This hypothesis tested whether e-commerce adoption has a significant effect on the performance of SMEs in Osun State. Results indicate a moderate positive correlation ($R = 0.506$) and that e-commerce adoption explains 25.6% of the variation in SME performance ($R^2 = 0.256$), with an adjusted R^2 of 0.123. The regression model is statistically significant ($F = 83.34$, $p < 0.001$), and e-commerce adoption positively influences SME performance ($B = 0.296$, $t = 6.64$, $p < 0.001$). These findings lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis, showing that SMEs adopting e-commerce platforms are likely to achieve better operational and financial performance outcomes compared to those that do not.

Testing of Hypothesis Two (H_{02}): There is no significant relationship between digital services and the performance of SMEs in Osun State.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.540	.292 a	.205	.901

Predictors: (Constant), Digital Services

Table 5: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	81.29	1	81.29	100.15	.000 ^b
	Residual	197.27	243	0.812		
	Total	278.56	244			

Dependent Variable: SMEs Performance

Predictors: (Constant), Digital Services

Table 6: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.870	.0058		32.24	.000
E-commerce	.313	.0420	.540	7.45	.000

Dependent Variable: SMEs Performance

Predictors: (Constant), Digital Services

Sources: Authors Computation, 2025.

The hypothesis tested the relationship between digital services and SME performance in Osun State. Results show a moderate positive correlation ($R = 0.540$), with digital services explaining 29.2% of the variation in SME performance ($R^2 = 0.292$). The regression model is statistically significant ($F = 100.15$, $p < 0.05$), and digital services have a significant positive effect on performance ($B = 0.313$, $t = 7.45$, $p < 0.05$). This indicates that increased use of digital services improves SME performance, leading to better efficiency, market reach, and financial outcomes. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Testing of Hypothesis Three (H_{03}): There is no significant relationship between software development and the performance of SMEs in Osun State.

Table 7: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.506 a	.256	.145	.934

a. Predictors: (Constant), Software development solutions

Table 8: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	72.95	1	72.95	83.69	.000
	Residual	211.95	243	0.872		
	Total	284.90	244			

Dependent Variable: SMEs Performance

Predictors: (Constant), Software development solutions

Table 9: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	0.886	0.101	-	8.77	.000
E-commerce	0.353	0.052	0.506	6.73	.000

Dependent Variable: SMEs Performance

Predictors: (Constant), Software development solutions

Sources: Authors Computation, 2025.

This hypothesis tested whether software development has a significant relationship with the performance of SMEs in Osun State. Results show a moderate positive correlation ($R = 0.506$) and that software development accounts for 25.6% of the variation in SME performance ($R^2 = 0.256$), with the remaining variation explained by other factors. The model is significant ($F = 83.69$, $p < 0.05$), and regression analysis indicates a positive effect of software development on SME performance ($B = 0.353$, $t = 6.73$, $p = 0.000$). The standardized beta (0.506) further confirms this moderate positive influence. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and it is concluded that SMEs that adopt software development solutions are likely to experience improved operational efficiency, data management, and overall performance compared to those that do not.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of digital entrepreneurship on the performance of SMEs in Osun State, Nigeria. The first hypothesis (H_1) assessed the effect of e-commerce adoption on SME performance. The findings support Oladele and Olupidi (2022), who reported that e-commerce improved retail sales performance, and align with Edokobi et al. (2022), who found that online sales, digital marketing, and e-payment systems enhanced SMEs' operational efficiency. However, this contrasts with Ochinanwata and Ochinanwata (2023), who noted that adoption may be constrained by low trust and skill gaps. Thus, SMEs adopting e-commerce platforms are more likely to improve operational and financial performance. This finding aligns with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), as SMEs adopt platforms perceived as easy to use and useful, such as WhatsApp, mobile banking, and POS systems, which simplify transactions and customer interaction. It also supports the Resource-Based View (RBV), as e-commerce functions as a strategic digital resource that enhances market reach and competitiveness. However, the relatively modest adjusted R^2 value suggests limited explanatory power, indicating that other factors such as infrastructure, digital literacy, access to finance, and policy support may also influence SME performance.

The second hypothesis (H₂) examined the relationship between digital services and SME performance. The findings are consistent with Olufemi et al. (2022) and Gregori and Holzmann (2020), who emphasized that digital tools such as cloud computing and online payments improve efficiency and competitiveness. SMEs that leverage digital services are therefore more likely to enhance operational efficiency, market reach, and financial outcomes. This aligns with TAM, as SMEs adopt services perceived as easy to use and useful, including mobile banking, POS, and USSD systems, and with RBV, since digital services serve as valuable organizational resources that strengthen operations and competitiveness. The stronger effect of digital services compared to e-commerce and software development may be due to their accessibility and ease of integration into daily business activities, as these tools require minimal technical expertise and are widely used in routine transactions.

The third hypothesis (H₃) assessed the effect of software development on SME performance. The results indicate that SMEs adopting software solutions can improve operational efficiency, data management, and overall business performance. This aligns with TAM, as SMEs adopt software perceived as useful and easy to use for managing business processes, and with RBV, as software development represents a strategic organizational resource that enhances operational capacity and competitive advantage. The finding is consistent with Omulo and Noor (2023), who reported a strong relationship between software development and SME performance in Nairobi, although the relationship observed in this study is more moderate, possibly due to differences in technological maturity and levels of adoption.

Conclusion and Recommendations: The study demonstrated that strategic adoption and integration of digital entrepreneurship tools, combined with skills development and supportive infrastructure, can enhance SME performance and competitiveness in Osun State. Based on the findings, this research suggests following measures:

1. SME owners should actively use platforms like WhatsApp, Instagram, TikTok and Jumia by consistently posting products, engaging customers through comments and responding promptly to inquiries to expand the market reach, boost sales and improve operational efficiency. They should also integrate interactive content such as videos, reels and customer testimonials to enhance visibility and customer engagement.
2. Continuous training programs should be developed by SME owners and their employees to improve their digital skills particularly in managing online platforms, interpreting analytics, applying customer engagement techniques, and managing these services effectively. These training programs should be conducted periodically through workshops, online courses, or partnerships with digital training institutions to ensure sustained skill development.

3. SMEs should adopt key performance indicators (KPIs) and analytics tools to continuously track the impact of digital tools on sales, customer satisfaction, and operational efficiency. This can be achieved by using analytics dashboards from platforms such as Meta Business Suite, Google Analytics, and e-commerce platform reports to support data-driven decision making,
4. The government and private sector should collaborate to provide reliable internet access, efficient delivery systems, and secure online payment gateways alongside improved power supply and robust cybersecurity frameworks to create a more enabling environment for digital entrepreneurship, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of e-commerce platforms. This collaboration will create an enabling environment for digital entrepreneurship and enhance the effectiveness of e-commerce platforms among SMEs.

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